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E- Governance, Judicial Efficiency and Service Delivery in the Rivers State Judiciary

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of e-governance on judicial efficiency and service delivery in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025. The study was anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which explains how perceived usefulness and ease of use influence technology adoption. A mixed-methods research design was adopted, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. The study population comprised judicial officers, court administrative staff, legal practitioners, and information technology personnel, from which a sample of 358 respondents was selected using the Yamane sampling formula. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and documentary sources. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were analysed through thematic content analysis. Findings revealed that e-governance significantly enhanced judicial efficiency and service delivery, with a grand mean score of 3.15 exceeding the benchmark of 2.50. The study found improvements in electronic case management, digital record keeping, communication, information accessibility, case tracking, and administrative productivity. However, its impact on reducing court adjournments remained limited. The study concluded that e-governance has substantially improved judicial efficiency and service delivery in the Rivers State Judiciary and recommended sustained investment in digital infrastructure, capacity building, integrated case management systems, and complementary procedural reforms.

Keywords: e-governance, judicial efficiency, Rivers State Judiciary, service delivery, Technology Acceptance Model.

INTRODUCTION

The use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in governance systems has transformed public service delivery across the world, giving rise to the concept of electronic governance (e-governance). E-governance refers to the application of electronic technologies in governmental operations to improve efficiency, transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in public administration (Abasilim *et al.*, 2016; Ogbonna, *et al.*, 2025). Within the judicial sector, e-governance represents a transition from traditional, paper-based judicial administration to technology-driven judicial processes (Shenkoya, 2023). This transformation is particularly significant in developing countries, where judicial systems often face challenges related to accessibility, efficiency, and public trust. Consequently, the global shift towards digital governance has created both opportunities and expectations for judicial reforms in countries such as Nigeria.

The Nigerian judiciary plays a critical role in the administration of justice, the interpretation of laws, and the preservation of the rule of law (Commonwealth Governance, 2014; Ogidi, *et al.*, 2024). Despite this constitutional responsibility, the judicial system has historically been characterized by

inefficiencies, prolonged case delays, limited access to justice, and allegations of corruption, all of which have undermined public confidence in the justice system (BTI Nigeria Country Report, 2024). Rivers State, one of Nigeria's economically strategic states located in the oil-rich Niger Delta region, possesses a complex judicial environment shaped by its vibrant commercial activities, diverse population, and socio-economic dynamics. For many years, the judiciary in the state has faced challenges such as case backlogs, manual record-keeping systems, limited public access to judicial information, and procedural delays that have impeded effective justice delivery (Dibie & Ya, 2020). As population growth and economic activities have increased, the demand for efficient judicial services has become more pressing, necessitating reforms aimed at modernizing judicial administration.

The rapid advancement of technology and the experience of the COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the global movement toward digitalization, highlighting the necessity for technology-driven judicial reforms. E-governance within the judiciary encompasses innovations such as electronic case management systems, electronic filing of court processes, virtual court proceedings, online access to judicial information, and digital payment platforms for court services (Inakefe *et al.*, 2023). These innovations are designed to streamline judicial procedures, reduce delays, improve transparency, and enhance public access to justice (Ajibade *et al.*, 2017). In support of digital transformation, the Nigerian government introduced policy frameworks such as the National Information Technology Policy and the National e-Government Master Plan to facilitate the adoption of digital technologies across public institutions, including the judiciary (Abdulkareem & Ishola, 2016; Ogbonna, *et al.*, 2025). These frameworks have provided strategic direction for digital governance initiatives at both federal and state levels.

The implementation of e-governance in the Rivers State Judiciary gained momentum from 2014 as part of broader efforts to modernize judicial administration and improve service delivery. This initiative aligned with national judicial reform programmes and increasing recognition of technology as a tool for addressing persistent challenges within the justice sector (Agbele *et al.*, 2012). Early reforms focused on automating fundamental court processes, establishing the judiciary's official website (www.judiciary.rv.gov.ng), and introducing electronic systems for case management to enhance administrative efficiency (Rivers State Judiciary, 2023). Subsequently, the judiciary adopted electronic filing systems, judicial information management platforms, virtual court proceedings, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, and digital payment systems for court-related transactions (Inakefe *et al.*, 2023). Over the period under study, these initiatives have evolved considerably through various technological interventions and infrastructural developments aimed at improving judicial service delivery.

The significance of e-governance in the Rivers State Judiciary extends beyond the mere adoption of technology. It represents a fundamental transformation in the manner judicial services are delivered. The primary objectives include improving access to justice, enhancing transparency, reducing opportunities for corruption, simplifying cumbersome procedures, and promoting greater efficiency in judicial operations (Wong & Welch, 2004). E-governance also offers the potential to bridge geographical and informational barriers that often prevent citizens, particularly those in rural and underserved communities, from accessing judicial services (Inakefe *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, digital platforms can strengthen accountability by creating electronic records and audit trails that make judicial processes more transparent and less susceptible to manipulation (Shenkoya, 2023). Nevertheless, significant disparities in access to technology and digital literacy between urban and rural populations remain important challenges that may limit the full realization of these benefits (UNDP Vietnam, 2023).

The legal and institutional framework supporting e-governance within the Rivers State Judiciary has evolved steadily to accommodate digital processes. Various legislative provisions, practice directions, and administrative guidelines have been developed to regulate electronic filing, virtual court proceedings, admissibility of electronic evidence, electronic signatures, and data protection mechanisms (Ajibade *et al.*, 2017). These legal frameworks have enhanced the legitimacy and reliability of digital judicial processes while ensuring that electronically generated records are recognized within the legal system (West, 2004). The Rivers State House of Assembly has contributed to creating an enabling environment through legislative interventions, while the executive arm of government has supported implementation through policy direction and resource allocation.

Such collaboration among stakeholders has been crucial in facilitating the digital transformation of the judiciary.

The adoption and effectiveness of e-governance are influenced by a variety of contextual factors, including political conditions, financial resources, technological infrastructure, digital literacy levels, and societal attitudes toward technology (Agbele *et al.*, 2012). Rivers State's status as a major economic hub provides opportunities for investment in digital infrastructure and judicial modernization initiatives. However, political developments, institutional dynamics, and broader governance reforms continue to influence the implementation and sustainability of e-governance projects. In addition, ongoing efforts to strengthen judicial autonomy and improve governance structures at both federal and state levels have implications for the pace and effectiveness of digital transformation within the judiciary.

Despite notable progress, the implementation of e-governance in the Rivers State Judiciary has encountered several challenges. These include inadequate technological infrastructure, insufficient technical expertise, limited funding, resistance to organizational change, cybersecurity concerns, and unequal access to digital services. The digital divide remains particularly significant, as many citizens lack the technological resources or skills required to effectively utilize digital judicial platforms (UNDP Vietnam, 2023). Research has also identified resistance among some judicial officers and court personnel as a major obstacle to the successful implementation of digital reforms (Ajibade *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, organizational, financial, and technological barriers continue to constrain efforts to fully digitalize judicial services (Agbele *et al.*, 2012). Nevertheless, the anticipated benefits including reduced case backlogs, faster case resolution, improved record management, greater access to legal information, and enhanced public confidence in the judiciary remain substantial (West, 2004). The COVID-19 pandemic served as a major catalyst for accelerating the adoption of e-governance within the Rivers State Judiciary. Restrictions associated with the pandemic disrupted conventional court operations and compelled judicial institutions to adopt virtual hearings, electronic filing systems, remote work arrangements, and digital communication platforms (Inakefe *et al.*, 2023). This experience demonstrated both the opportunities and limitations of digital judicial administration during periods of crisis. It also underscored the importance of digital resilience and institutional preparedness for ensuring continuity of judicial services under emergency conditions (World Bank, 2020). Existing digital transformation initiatives prior to the pandemic enabled courts to adapt more effectively to these unprecedented challenges (Ajibade *et al.*, 2017).

Looking ahead, the future of e-governance in the Rivers State Judiciary is likely to be shaped by emerging technologies, changing citizen expectations, evolving legal frameworks, and lessons learned from implementation experiences. Innovations such as Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain technology, and advanced data analytics have the potential to further enhance judicial efficiency, transparency, and service delivery, although they also raise important legal, ethical, and regulatory concerns (Electronic Governance in Nigeria, 2022). Sustained political commitment, adequate funding, continuous capacity development, and investment in digital infrastructure will be essential for consolidating existing gains and ensuring the long-term sustainability of e-governance initiatives (Shenkoya, 2023). Greater integration between the judiciary and other arms of government may also facilitate more seamless digital service delivery and improve citizens' experiences in accessing justice (Ajibade *et al.*, 2017).

Against this background, this study poses a research question thus: How effective has e-governance been in enhancing the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025?

This study is significant because it provides empirical evidence on the effectiveness of e-governance in enhancing the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025. The findings will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on digital governance and judicial reform in Nigeria. The study will also be useful to policymakers, judicial administrators, legislators, and development partners by identifying the achievements, challenges, and opportunities associated with judicial digitalization. Furthermore, it will provide practical recommendations for improving service delivery, reducing procedural delays, strengthening transparency, and promoting greater access to justice through technology-driven judicial administration.

Theoretical Framework: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Fred Davis (1989) as an adaptation of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975). The model was introduced to explain and predict individuals' acceptance and use of information technology. Davis' seminal work, *Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology* (1989), established TAM as one of the most influential theories in information systems research. Subsequent studies by Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw (1989) empirically validated the model and clarified the relationships among its principal constructs. The model was later extended through TAM2 by Venkatesh and Davis (2000), which incorporated social influence and cognitive instrumental processes, and subsequently contributed to the development of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) by Venkatesh et al. (2003).

The central proposition of TAM is that an individual's intention to use a technological system is primarily determined by two factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness refers to the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will enhance job performance, while perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which the technology is perceived as effortless to use (Davis, 1989). These perceptions influence users' attitudes and behavioural intentions, which subsequently determine actual technology usage.

TAM is founded on several key assumptions. First, individuals are rational decision-makers who evaluate the expected benefits and costs associated with adopting a technology before deciding whether to use it (Davis, 1989). Second, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are distinct but related constructs, with ease of use influencing usefulness because users are more likely to perceive a system as beneficial when it is easy to operate (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989). Third, external variables such as system design, organizational support, training, technological infrastructure, and user characteristics affect technology adoption indirectly through their influence on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use rather than directly influencing usage behaviour (Venkatesh & Davis, 1996). Finally, TAM assumes that the relationships among its key constructs remain relatively stable across different technological contexts and user groups, although their relative influence may vary (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

The theoretical foundation of TAM rests on several interrelated principles. The first is the principle of perceived usefulness, which suggests that users are more likely to adopt technologies they believe will improve their performance and productivity. The second is the principle of perceived ease of use, which posits that technologies requiring less effort are more likely to be accepted by users. A third principle is behavioural intention, which serves as the immediate determinant of actual system use. According to TAM, behavioural intention mediates the relationship between user perceptions and actual technology adoption (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). The model also recognizes the role of external variables, which shape users' perceptions of usefulness and ease of use. Furthermore, cognitive instrumental processes influence users' assessments of technological value through considerations such as job relevance, output quality, and the demonstrability of results (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Despite its widespread acceptance and extensive empirical validation, TAM has been subject to criticism. Scholars have argued that the model provides a relatively narrow explanation of technology adoption by focusing primarily on usefulness and ease of use while paying limited attention to social, cultural, emotional, and institutional influences (Bagozzi, 2007). Others contend that TAM overemphasizes rational decision-making and fails to adequately account for habitual behaviour, organizational politics, and contextual factors that may influence technology acceptance (Benbasat & Barki, 2007). The model has also been criticized for its limited explanatory power in environments characterized by mandatory technology use, complex organizational structures, and diverse cultural settings (Lee, Kozar, & Larsen, 2003). Consequently, scholars have recommended complementing TAM with broader organizational and institutional theories, such as Institutional Theory and New Public Management, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of technological change within public sector organizations (Avgerou, 2010).

The relevance of TAM to this study lies in its ability to explain how stakeholders within the Rivers State Judiciary perceive and adopt e-governance technologies. The implementation of digital innovations such as electronic case filing systems, digital records management platforms, virtual court proceedings, and online judicial information services depends largely on the willingness of judges,

court personnel, legal practitioners, and court users to embrace these technologies. TAM provides a useful framework for examining how perceptions of usefulness and ease of use influence the acceptance and utilization of these digital systems (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

Furthermore, the model's emphasis on behavioural intention enables the study to assess whether positive attitudes toward e-governance translate into actual usage of digital judicial services. Through TAM, factors such as technological infrastructure, user competence, training opportunities, organizational support, and system quality can be analysed as external variables influencing technology adoption within the judiciary. This perspective is particularly important in understanding the extent to which e-governance initiatives have contributed to improving the efficiency of judicial processes in Rivers State between 2014 and 2025.

The application of TAM in this study therefore provides a valuable analytical lens for assessing the effectiveness of e-governance in the Rivers State Judiciary. The model facilitates an examination of how stakeholders perceive the usefulness of e-governance technologies in enhancing efficiency, reducing delays, improving access to information, and strengthening service delivery. It also enables an assessment of how ease of use influences the willingness of users to engage with digital judicial platforms. By analysing the effects of external variables such as infrastructure availability, capacity-building initiatives, organizational support, and technological literacy, TAM offers insights into the factors that promote or hinder successful e-governance implementation.

When integrated with Institutional Theory and New Public Management, TAM provides a comprehensive framework for understanding both individual-level technology acceptance and broader institutional transformation. This combined perspective enhances the study's ability to explain how e-governance has influenced judicial efficiency, administrative modernization, and service delivery within the Rivers State Judiciary during the period under investigation.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of e-governance in enhancing judicial efficiency in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025. The mixed-methods approach was considered appropriate because it enabled the collection of numerical data on the outcomes of e-governance implementation while also capturing stakeholders' experiences, perceptions, and contextual insights (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

The population of the study comprised key stakeholders involved in or affected by e-governance initiatives in the Rivers State Judiciary, including judicial officers, court administrative staff, legal practitioners, and implementation stakeholders. The accessible population was 3,320 respondents drawn from the official records of the Rivers State Judiciary Staff Biometric Register (2025) and the Nigerian Bar Association, Port Harcourt Branch. Using the Yamane (1967) formula at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, a sample size of 358 respondents was determined. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure proportionate representation of all stakeholder categories, while purposive sampling was used to select key informants for interviews.

The distribution of the population of the study stakeholders is shown in Table 3.1.

S/N	Stakeholder Category	Sub-Category	Number	% of Total Accessible Population
1	Judicial Officers	High Court Judges	42	1.27%
		Customary Court of Appeal Judges	18	0.54%
		Chief Magistrates	25	0.75%
		Sub-total	85	2.56%
2	Court Staff	Administrative Court Registrars	68	2.05%

S/N	Stakeholder Category	Sub-Category	Number	% of Total Accessible Population
		Court Clerks	142	4.28%
		IT Personnel	28	0.84%
		Other Administrative Staff	182	5.48%
		Sub-total	420	12.65%
3	Legal Practitioners	Registered Practicing Lawyers (NBA PHC Branch)	2,750	82.83%
		Sub-total	2,750	82.83%
4	Implementation Stakeholders	Internal ICT Staff	18	0.54%
		External IT Contractors	22	0.66%
		Policy Advisors and Consultants	15	0.45%
		Donor Partner Representatives	10	0.30%
		Sub-total	65	1.96%
TOTAL (Accessible Population)			3,320	100%

Source: Rivers State Judiciary Staff Biometric Register (August 2025).

Data were collected through two principal instruments: a structured questionnaire titled *E-Governance and Judicial Service Delivery Questionnaire (EGJSDQ)* and a secondary source. The questionnaire contained items measured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1)

To ensure validity, the instruments were subjected to face and content validation by experts in Political Science, Public Administration, Information Systems, and Measurement and Evaluation. Their observations and recommendations were incorporated before the final administration of the instruments. Reliability of the questionnaire was established through a pilot study involving 30 respondents outside the study area. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained, indicating a high level of internal consistency.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 was used for quantitative analysis, and findings were presented using tables and charts.

DATA PRESENTATION

This part presents the results of the field survey, analyses the results in terms of the five research questions and hypotheses, and discusses the results in light of the theories selected and the empirical literature reviewed in Chapter Two. The study examined the theme of e-governance and its impact on service delivery in the Rivers State Judiciary during the period 2014 to 2025 under the following thematic areas: the effect of e-governance on the efficiency of judicial process, reducing corruption, enhancing accessibility and access to justice, challenges in implementation, and measures for the protection of data as part of platform sustainability.

The administration and return rates of questionnaires are provided in the table below:

Table 1: Analysis of distributed and returned questionnaires

S/N	Stakeholder Category	Copies Administered	Copies Retrieved & Valid	Return (%)	Rate
1	Judicial Officers	20	20	100.0%	
2	Court Administrative Staff	84	81	96.4%	
3	Legal Practitioners	275	265	96.4%	
4	Court Users / Litigants	65	61	93.8%	
5	Implementation Stakeholders	14	14	100.0%	
	Total	458	441	96.3%	

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Five categories of stakeholders including 458 copies of the structured questionnaire were reached. Of the 441 retrieved and valid, 96.3% responded. Answers were marked on a 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree = 4, Agree = 3, Disagree = 2 and Strongly Disagree = 1) and a mean score of 2.50 was used as the decision threshold. The five null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. A total number of 45 semi-structured interviews were conducted between March 2026 and gather qualitative data.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
1.	Male	254	57.6%	57.6%
2.	Female	178	40.4%	98.0%
3.	Prefer not to say	9	2.0%	100.0%
	Total	441	100.0%	

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Table 2 reveals that 254 respondents (57.6%) were male and 178 (40.4%) were female. The results show that the majority of the respondents were male, which is in line with the historical gender ratio of legal professions in Nigeria (Ajibade et al., 2017), and that the female respondents, at 40.4% is in line with the trends of the past few years as it relates to gender inclusion in judicial institutions in Rivers State (Inakefe et al., 2023).

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Age Group

S/N	Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	25-35 years	98	22.2%	22.2%
2	36-45 years	167	37.9%	60.1%
3	46-55 years	134	30.4%	90.5%
4	56-65 years	35	7.9%	98.4%
5	Above 65 years	7	1.6%	100.0%
	Total	441	100.0%	

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Table 3 indicates that most of the respondents were aged 36 to 45 years, followed by 46 to 55 years (30.4%). The concentration of the age group 36-55 years shows that this age range has a great deal of judicial experience to support informed comparative evaluation before and after the implementation of electronic-governance (Dibie & Ya, 2020).

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

S/N	Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	Secondary School Certificate	18	4.1%	4.1%
2	National Diploma/NCE	29	6.6%	10.7%
3	Bachelor's Degree	183	41.5%	52.2%
4	Master's Degree	168	38.1%	90.3%
5	PhD/Doctorate	43	9.7%	100.0%
	Total	441	100.0%	

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

As shown in Table 4, 183 respondents (41.5%) had a Bachelor's Degree while 168 respondents (38.1%) had a Master's Degree, making up 79.6% of the respondents. A high percentage of tertiary education helps to validate the self-reported perceptions obtained from the instrument (Davis, 1989).

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents by Years of Experience with the Rivers State Judiciary

S/N	Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	Less than 2 years	31	7.0%	7.0%
2	2-5 years	62	14.1%	21.1%
3	6-10 years	109	24.7%	45.8%
4	11-15 years	124	28.1%	73.9%
5	16-20 years	78	17.7%	91.6%
6	More than 20 years	37	8.4%	100.0%
	Total	441	100.0%	

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Table 5 reveals that 124 respondents (28.1%) had 11-15 years of experience, and 109 (24.7%) had 6-10 years. Most of them (78.9%) served for at least six years in the Rivers State Judiciary, making them good informants of the trajectory of implementation of e-governance from 2014 onward.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question: How has e-governance affected the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025?

To answer this research question, respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with ten statements relating to the impact of e-governance on the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary.

Table 6: shows the impact of e-governance on the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev	Decision
1	E-governance has significantly reduced case processing times in Rivers State courts	187	173	57	24	3.19	0.87	Accepted
2	Electronic case management systems have improved file retrieval efficiency	201	168	49	23	3.24	0.84	Accepted
3	Digital documentation has reduced paperwork and	194	162	58	27	3.19	0.88	Accepted

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev	Decision
	administrative burdens							
4	Online case tracking allows better monitoring of case progress	176	181	54	30	3.14	0.87	Accepted
5	E-governance has reduced court adjournments due to administrative issues	153	178	72	38	3.01	0.91	Accepted
6	Electronic systems have improved scheduling and calendar management	168	172	68	33	3.08	0.89	Accepted
7	Digital platforms have enhanced communication between court staff and users	173	176	60	32	3.11	0.88	Accepted
8	E-governance has improved overall productivity in court operations	181	169	61	30	3.14	0.87	Accepted
9	Automated processes have reduced human errors in court procedures	189	164	57	31	3.16	0.87	Accepted
10	Digital record keeping has improved data accuracy and consistency	196	166	52	27	3.20	0.85	Accepted
	Grand Mean					3.15	0.87	Accepted (Overall)

Note: SA=Strongly Agree (4), A=Agree (3), D=Disagree (2), SD=Strongly Disagree (1). Mean \geq 2.50 = Accepted; Mean $<$ 2.50 = Rejected.

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

The data presented in Table 4.6 reveal respondents' perceptions of the impact of e-governance on the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025. The results indicate that all ten items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, demonstrating a strong consensus among respondents that e-governance has positively influenced judicial efficiency. The item means ranged from 3.01 to 3.24, while the grand mean of 3.15 with a standard deviation of 0.87 indicates a generally favourable assessment of the efficiency gains associated with e-governance initiatives.

The highest-rated item was the improvement in file retrieval efficiency through electronic case management systems (Mean = 3.24, SD = 0.84), followed by improved data accuracy and consistency through digital record keeping (Mean = 3.20, SD = 0.85), and reduction in case processing time (Mean = 3.19, SD = 0.87). These findings suggest that respondents perceived the greatest benefits of e-governance in areas relating to case management, records administration, and information processing. Similarly, reductions in paperwork and administrative burdens (Mean = 3.19) and reductions in human errors through automated processes (Mean = 3.16) further underscore the contribution of digital technologies to administrative efficiency within the judiciary.

Although all items were positively rated, the reduction of court adjournments due to administrative issues recorded the lowest mean score (Mean = 3.01, SD = 0.91). This finding suggests that while e-governance has addressed several administrative bottlenecks, other factors responsible for adjournments, such as the absence of counsel, witness-related challenges, and procedural constraints, may persist beyond the scope of digital interventions. The relatively higher standard deviation for this item also indicates greater variation in respondents' experiences and perceptions.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study demonstrate that e-governance has significantly enhanced the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025. The grand mean score of 3.15, which exceeds the criterion mean of 2.50, indicates strong positive perceptions among respondents regarding the contribution of digital technologies to judicial administration. Specifically, improvements in file retrieval, digital record management, case tracking, scheduling, communication, and overall court productivity suggest that the adoption of e-governance has facilitated faster, more accurate, and more efficient judicial operations. These findings imply that the introduction of digital platforms has reduced many of the administrative bottlenecks traditionally associated with manual judicial processes.

The findings are consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1989), which posits that users are more likely to adopt technologies they perceive as useful and easy to use. The high ratings recorded across all ten indicators suggest that judges, court staff, legal practitioners, and other stakeholders recognize the practical benefits of e-governance systems in improving work performance and service delivery. The positive perceptions of electronic case management systems, digital record keeping, and online tracking platforms indicate that stakeholders have largely accepted these technologies as essential tools for enhancing judicial efficiency.

The results also corroborate empirical evidence from other jurisdictions. For example, the introduction of the Integrated Electronic Case Management System (IECMS) by the Kenyan Judiciary significantly improved case management efficiency, reduced paperwork, and enhanced access to judicial information. Similarly, the Judiciary of England and Wales reported substantial improvements in case processing and administrative efficiency following the implementation of digital court reforms and online filing systems. In Nigeria, the introduction of virtual court proceedings and electronic filing systems by the Lagos State Judiciary during and after the COVID-19 pandemic contributed to the continuity of judicial services and reduced delays associated with physical court processes. These examples demonstrate that digital technologies can enhance the speed, accuracy, and effectiveness of judicial administration when adequately implemented.

The finding that electronic case management systems recorded the highest mean score (3.24) is particularly significant because efficient file retrieval and case management are central to effective justice delivery. Manual record-keeping systems often result in misplaced files, duplication of records, and delays in accessing information. By contrast, digital systems provide real-time access to case files, facilitate case tracking, and improve coordination among judicial personnel. Likewise, the high mean scores recorded for digital record keeping (3.20) and reduced case processing time (3.19) indicate that respondents perceive technology as a critical tool for enhancing accuracy and expediting judicial processes.

Despite these positive outcomes, the relatively lower mean score recorded for the reduction of court adjournments (3.01) reveals important limitations of e-governance. While technology can address administrative causes of delay, many adjournments arise from factors such as the absence of counsel, unavailability of witnesses, procedural complexities, and compliance with legal requirements. Consequently, technological innovations alone may not completely eliminate delays in judicial proceedings. This finding supports the argument of New Public Management scholars that technology-driven reforms must be complemented by institutional restructuring, process re-engineering, and human capacity development to achieve optimal performance outcomes (Hood, 1991).

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of e-governance on the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary between 2014 and 2025. The findings revealed that e-governance has made a significant positive contribution to judicial efficiency, as evidenced by the grand mean score of 3.15, which exceeded the acceptance benchmark of 2.50. Respondents generally agreed that digital technologies have improved file retrieval, reduced paperwork, enhanced data accuracy, strengthened case tracking, improved communication among stakeholders, and increased overall productivity in court operations. The study established that electronic case management systems and digital record-keeping mechanisms have become critical tools for improving administrative efficiency and service delivery within the judiciary.

The findings further demonstrated that the adoption of e-governance has facilitated faster and more reliable access to judicial information, reduced opportunities for administrative errors, and improved the management of court records. These outcomes support the proposition of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) that technologies perceived as useful and easy to use are more likely to be accepted and effectively utilized by stakeholders. However, the study also revealed that e-governance has had a relatively limited impact on reducing court adjournments, suggesting that many delays in judicial proceedings arise from procedural, institutional, and human factors beyond the scope of technological solutions alone.

Overall, the study concludes that e-governance has substantially enhanced the efficiency of judicial processes in the Rivers State Judiciary. Nevertheless, the sustainability and effectiveness of these gains depend on continuous investment in technological infrastructure, human capacity development, institutional reforms, and stakeholder support mechanisms. Achieving a fully efficient digital judiciary requires a holistic approach that integrates technological innovation with procedural and organizational improvements.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Rivers State Judiciary should sustain and expand its e-governance initiatives by investing in modern digital technologies, infrastructure, and support systems to further enhance the efficiency of judicial processes and improve service delivery across all courts in the state.

Electronic case management and digital record-keeping systems should be fully integrated and strengthened across all judicial divisions to improve file retrieval, case tracking, data accuracy, records management, and overall administrative efficiency.

The Judiciary should enhance the use of digital communication and information management platforms by providing continuous training for judicial officers, court staff, legal practitioners, and court users to maximize the benefits of improved communication, scheduling, productivity, and access to judicial information.

The Rivers State Judiciary should complement e-governance reforms with broader procedural and institutional reforms aimed at reducing court delays. Measures such as stricter case-flow management, improved witness coordination, enforcement of timelines for legal practitioners, and reforms in adjournment practices should be implemented to address non-technological causes of delay and improve the speed of justice delivery. I have removed duplicate entries, arranged the references

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